

DIAMOND-LIKE COATING AND COMPARISON OF TURNING CUTS WITH WITH DIFFERENT COATINGS

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Annotation. The article discusses modern coating methods. An analysis of the unique properties and characteristics of turning tools with different coatings is presented.

Keywords: Tribological properties, wear resistance CVD, PVD coating, diamond-like coating, graphite-like bonds, carbide, roughness.

Introduction.

For many years, researchers and industrialists have been concerned with optimizing and improving tribological properties. Tribological process is wear that occurs when two surfaces come into contact and both or one of them moves relative to each other. By reducing friction and wear by 15-20%, economic efficiency can be significantly increased.

In order to obtain high wear resistance of a surface with an ultra-low coefficient of friction, without losing high mechanical properties, there are several tribological systems [1,3,4]. One of the most common methods of strengthening a substrate material without changing its properties and obtaining high wear resistance is the use of coatings.

Tools of any geometric complexity can be coated. The most common material for making tools is carbide. The discovery of applying wear-resistant coatings using the ion plasma method has become a new achievement in the manufacture of cutting tools.

Main part

To harden products, two methods are presented: the chemical deposition method (Chemical Vapour Deposition - CVD) and the method of physical deposition of coatings (Physical Vapour Deposition - PVD).

PVD coating method is widely used to harden cutting tools. This method has found wide application in industry, since the chemical method of coating deposition involves constant monitoring of chemical reaction products and the use of expensive chemical reagents. Physical deposition of coatings using an arc

discharge allows for minor deviations in process parameters and allows for high productivity. Currently, when coating by physical deposition, titanium or its alloys are used, which are applied by ion sputtering or evaporation [6].

Depending on the speed and flow density of the sprayed material, what coating application modes will be, what preparatory work will be done before the application process, and even on the configuration of the technological equipment, the cutting properties, as well as the structure and adhesion of the tool coating, will depend.

Initially, TiN coatings began to be used in production. This coating provided high economic efficiency. After the successful application of a single-layer coating, double-layer coatings began to be created, consisting of titanium carbide TiC or titanium carbonitride TiCN and a thin surface layer of aluminum oxide Al₂O₃ deposited in the appropriate sequence.

An alternative option was multilayer coatings such as TiCN/TiN. When applying multilayer coatings, no layers are actually formed. Modern coating methods make it possible not to create interphase boundaries between layers and even between the coating and the surface being coated. Such coatings have high impact strength, are resistant to cracking, and have a lower level of internal stresses due to equalization of thermal expansion coefficients. For example, TiCN coating has a multilayer two-phase structure TiN-TiCN, which increases the strength and machining characteristics compared to TiN coating.

Somewhat later, combinations of different coatings and the use of external coatings such as TiAlN began to be developed and used. Such coatings provided good chip removal. The highest wear resistance indicators are present in high-hard diamond-like coatings (DLC). In addition to high wear resistance, these coatings have a low coefficient of friction. However, despite such advantages, these coatings have a high level of internal stress. Diamond-like coating (DLC) is a technology of plasma pulse sputtering of graphite in a vacuum chamber and deposition of carbon ions with sufficiently high energy on products. It comes in seven different forms. All seven contain significant amounts of sp³ hybridized carbon atoms.

APC consists of carbon atoms with both diamond-like and graphite-like bonds, which significantly increases the service life of products with such coating. [7].

With the discovery and development of new methods of metal processing, it was revealed that the use of new tool materials is one of the most rational methods for achieving increased productivity. To ensure that the cutting tool

lasts for a long time. If it remained functional, it is necessary that the applied coating provides good durability and hardness.

Enterprises need to use new equipment, update and improve product manufacturing technologies, and achieve improved quality of products in order to be competitive.

For that to be processed ensuring high productivity necessary used modern metal-cutting tools combined with high-tech CNC equipment.

Carbide tools operate at cutting speeds up to 300 m/min. At the same time, drills have a speed of 50 to 70 m/min, and modern developments allow drills to reach speeds of 90 to 180 m/min. The spindle rotation speed reaches up to 10,000 rpm. In order to improve the mechanical properties of the tool, manufacturers use an alloy with fine grains.

The tool with and without coating is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Coated and uncoated tool.

CVD Coated Carbide Grades

- high adhesion of the coating and the base;
- have high wear resistance and have properties that prevent the formation of build-up;
- choice for roughing of stainless steels; - structural and low-carbon steels are processed with high efficiency;
- when processing difficult-to-machine materials, high wear resistance is observed.

Uncoated carbide alloys

A hard alloy is a tool material that is produced by powder metallurgy, based on titanium, tantalum, tungsten carbide, using a cobalt binder (TaC, TiC, WC and Co). CVD coating improves tool strength, wear resistance, and ability to withstand high temperatures. For groups P, M, K there is an advantage, since it is possible to use a wide range of brands; produce replaceable polyhedral plates with high accuracy of geometric dimensions.

PVD coated carbide grades

- when processing heat-resistant steels, cast irons, stainless steels, efficiency increases;
- the tool's cutting edge strength increases due to the fine-grained base with high hardness;
- the tool is not subject to oxidative wear.

When comparing ultra-fine-grain carbide and medium-grain carbide, the former has higher mechanical strength. Thanks to this, it is possible to significantly increase the cutting speed. The characteristics of such an alloy are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Characteristics of ultra-fine-grained alloy

Hard alloys with APP coating

- tool life increases by 150%;
- between the front surface of the replaceable multifaceted coated plate and the chips, the coefficient of friction is reduced;
- build-up formation decreases;
- the quality of the processed surface increases;

DLC coated carbide grades

Carbide alloys with a diamond-like coating make it possible to obtain high quality metal processing, since they have a low coefficient of friction on the rake surface of <0.1 . When processing non-ferrous metals, high tool life is ensured. Most often, APP is used for hardening end mills, drills, and turning tools with replaceable carbide inserts. Coated tools are used when processing materials such as wood, aluminum, and plastic [5,2]. The roughness of machined parts using carbide and DLC tools is shown in Figure 4.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the work, we can highlight the properties of the

most common coatings, which are presented in Table 1.

Properties of the most common coatings.

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